

AN ALGORITHM FOR THE ANALYSIS OF CRITICAL STRESSES IN
CONTINUOUS FILAMENT REINFORCED FLAT PLATES SUBJECTED
TO UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPRESSIVE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The problem of predicting failure in continuous fiber reinforced flat plates under unidirectional compressive loading for both unidirectional and bidirectional fiber lay-ups is considered. Microbuckling in transversely supported fibers is presented as the failure mechanism for certain composite plates. This mechanism is applicable to plates in which fiber and resin properties allow microbuckling at stresses below smeared property global buckling and compressive strength limits. An energy method for calculating microbuckling stresses is presented. Finite element analysis methods utilizing fiber and resin properties are employed to evaluate composite mechanical properties and transverse stiffness. Microbuckling stresses for compression loaded carbon/epoxy and fiberglass/epoxy flat plate samples of various thicknesses are predicted and compared with experimental results. Reasonable correlation is observed, including reduction in ultimate stress with increasing wall thickness.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the development of primary and secondary structural components for high performance mechanisms, the design objective is maximum strength-to-weight ratio integrated with optimal acoustic energy damping; efficient thermal energy management; minimized degradation from environmental effects; and optimal reliability. The first step toward achieving this goal is the selection and analysis of materials and geometries which will provide structural integrity at elevated strength-to-weight ratios. To this end, material research and development efforts point toward continuous fiber reinforced metallic or non-metallic composite materials. However, the structural response of this type of material, when subjected to compressive loading and/or bending moments, is not well understood.

Addressed herein, is the problem of predicting failure in continuous fiber reinforced flat plates under unidirectional compressive loading for both unidirectional and bidirectional

fiber lay-ups. See figures (1) and (2). Solving the fiber reinforced flat plate compression problem is basic to developing a general analysis for predicting compressive failure loads in continuous fiber reinforced composites. Microbuckling in transversely supported fibers is presented as the failure mechanism for certain composite plates. This mechanism is applicable to plates in which fiber and resin properties cause microbuckling at stresses below smeared property global buckling and compressive strength predictions. An energy method for calculating microbuckling stresses is presented. Finite element analysis methods utilizing fiber and resin properties are employed to evaluate composite mechanical properties and transverse stiffness. Microbuckling stresses for carbon/epoxy and fiberglass/epoxy flat plate samples of various thicknesses are predicted and compared with experimental results. Reasonable correlation is presented without the introduction of micromechanical non-linearities based on a priori information.

FIGURE 1. UNIDIRECTIONAL CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE SUBJECTED TO COMPRESSIVE LOADING

FIGURE 2. [0/0/90] CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE SUBJECTED TO COMPRESSIVE LOADING

2. ANALYSIS

2.1 Failure Mechanisms For a composite with unidirectional continuous fibers, it has been suggested that the upper bound of compressive strength should approach the tensile strength of the reinforcing fibers. Generally, this has not been observed. Given that there are no macroscopic anomalies, it is usually assumed that the inability to reach the "upper bound" of compressive strength is due to imperfections in the fiber/matrix continuum at the micromechanical level. At the present time, there is no general analysis which accurately predicts reduced compressive strength due to micromechanical anomalies, and it is not clear as to what affect these anomalies have on ultimate strength.

Other phenomena which are even more perplexing are reduced compressive strength with increased wall thickness and dramatic dissimilarities in compressive strength given differences in filament lay-up, geometry, and loading format. For example, filament wound circular cylinders subjected to biaxial compression with bending moments superimposed have been observed to fail at strength levels significantly lower than flat plate

samples subjected to unidirectional compression. This phenomenon is not observed in isotropic homogeneous materials.

There have been several attempts to explain the phenomena observed with respect to compressive failure in fiber reinforced composites. One school of thought proposes that transverse splitting or debonding is the precursor to global failure. Simply stated, the transverse expansion strain, as a result of longitudinal compression, may exceed the ultimate strain capability of the composite. See reference [1]. While this theory seems reasonable, it has two flaws. It appears to work well only with material and geometry specific laminated composite samples which demonstrate ultimate strains in the neighborhood of .00127 cm/cm and it does not predict the fall off in ultimate strength in flat plates and circular cylinders regularly observed with increasing wall thickness.

A second theory, Rosen, Hahn, et al, references [2] thru [6], proposes that microbuckling is the failure criterion or at least the precursor to global failure in certain continuous fiber reinforced composites. This criterion is applicable to composites in which fiber and resin properties allow microbuckling at stresses below global buckling and compressive strength levels. The theory is that microbuckling leads to either fiber delamination/debonding for non-brittle fibers in non-brittle resins or to kinking for brittle fibers in non-brittle resins.

Figure (3) shows the two commonly accepted forms of microbuckling, "In-phase" and "Out-of-phase". The "In-phase" buckle requires less energy per fiber to initiate, and is usually assumed to be the mode of buckling in composites that have significant fiber content, $v_f > 40$ to 50%. Compressive applications for unidirectional fiber reinforced composites with significant fiber volume are the more common and, as such, are of greater interest.

Figure (4) depicts fiber failure or fracture along kink plains. Some researchers feel that kinking is a basic failure mode for brittle fibers such as carbon/graphite fibers, and that kinking initiates at some microscopic anomaly such as a void in the matrix. A domino effect then takes over and the part proceeds to global failure. Other researchers remain consistent in that microbuckling is the primary mode of failure and that in brittle fiber composites, microbuckling is the precursor to kinking with global failure already underway when kinking initiates.

There are three other failure modes that are considered with respect to continuous fiber reinforced composites, shear crippling, compression failure and global buckling. Macroscopically, shear crippling looks like a classic shear failure at some angle with the direction of loading; but microscopically, it looks suspiciously like a kink band. Compression failure occurs when the matrix stiffness is great enough to prevent microbuckling. Its fracture surfaces are generally oriented at 45° with respect to the loading, and are characterized by clean fractures without kinking. Global buckling occurs when component geometry precludes compressive failure and matrix stiffness precludes microbuckling. It is characterized by the classic instability failure form associated with the geometry under analysis.

Figure 3. Microbuckling under Compressive Loading

Figure 4. Kink Bands (Brittle Fiber failure)

2.2 Classical Micromechanical Modeling for "In-Phase" Fiber Buckling in Continuous Fiber Reinforced Composites Consider a fiber embedded in a fiber/matrix continuum. Figure (5) is a free-body diagram of a small segment, length dx.

- P = axial compressive force
- Q = transverse shear
- M = bending moment
- p = applied distributed axial force
- q = applied distributed transverse force
- m = applied distributed bending moment

Figure 5. Small Segment of Fiber in Equilibrium

Assuming small deflections, the initial fiber axis to be along the x-axis, and second order terms to be neglected, the equilibrium equations are written as

$$\sum F_x = p - \frac{dP}{dx} + Q \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} = 0 \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\sum F_y = q + \frac{dQ}{dx} + P \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} = 0 \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\sum M = \frac{dM}{dx} - Q + m = 0 \quad \dots (3)$$

The model of a fiber surrounded by an infinite continuum has been solved within the framework of elasticity. The combination of equations (2) and (3) for q = non-zero, P = constant and p = m = 0 leads to

$$S_{Cr} = \frac{G_m}{1 - \nu_f} + \frac{E_f I_f}{A_f} \left[\frac{\pi}{L} \right]^2 \quad \dots (4)$$

where S_{cr} is critical buckling stress, G_m is matrix shear modulus, v_f^{cr} is fiber volume fraction, A_f^m is fiber cross-section, L is fiber length, E_f is fiber modulus of elasticity and I_f is fiber area moment of inertia. See reference [2]. Equation (4) is generally known to yield much higher strengths than is realized experimentally. See figures (6) and (7) for comparisons of equation (4) (second term neglected) with experimental data. See references [7] and [8] for experimental data.

Several improvements and modifications have been suggested since reference (2) was published. Most include the incorporation of initial fiber curvature (wavy fibers) and material non-linearities (resin rich regions, voids, etc.). Consider the inclusion of initial fiber curvature in the "In-phase" buckle model. For m and q non-zero, $P = \text{constant}$ and $p = 0$. Equations (1), (2) and (3) lead to

$$S_{cr} = v_f \left[G_c + \frac{E_f I_f}{A_f L} \left[\frac{\pi}{L} \right]^2 + \frac{K}{A_f} \left[\frac{L}{\pi} \right]^2 \right] \left[1 - \frac{F_0}{F} \right] \quad \dots (5)$$

Where $G_c = G_m / (1 - v_f)$, K is a constant of proportionality characterizing q , F_0 is initial fiber curvature amplitude and F is microbuckle wave amplitude. See reference [3].

When compared to equation (4), equation (5) reduces the level of critical stress by the factor v_f (the result of assuming a non-zero q). The introduction of initially curved fibers also reduces critical stress when the curvature is of the order of the fiber buckle curvature. However, similar orders of curvature is not the norm. Thus, the effect of precurved fibers is negligible. See figures (6) and (7) for comparisons of equation (5) (first term only) with equation (4) and experimental data, references [7] and [8].

FIG 6. CRITICAL COMPRESSIVE STRESS
S-2 FIBERGLASS/3501-6 EPOXY (60/40)

FIG 7. CRITICAL COMPRESSIVE STRESS
AS4 GRAPHITE/3501-6 EPOXY (60/40)

- + ROSEN [1]
- + HAHN & WILLIAMS [2]
- UNIDIRECT-EXP. [6]
- [0/0/90]-EXP. [6]

2.3 An Energy Method for Calculating Microbuckling Loads in Continuous Fiber Reinforced Composites As an alternative to equations (4) & (5), consider the buckling of a transversely supported fiber in a fiber/matrix continuum subjected to an axial compression load. See reference [9].

Figure 8. Buckling of a Fiber in an Elastic Continuum

The general expression for the deflection curve shown can be represented by the series

$$y = a_1 \sin\left[\frac{\pi x}{L}\right] + a_2 \sin\left[\frac{2\pi x}{L}\right] + a_3 \sin\left[\frac{3\pi x}{L}\right] + \dots$$

The strain energy of bending of the fiber is

$$\Delta U_1 = \frac{E_f I_f}{2} \int_0^L \left[\frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} \right]^2 dx$$

$$\Delta U_1 = \frac{\pi^4 E_f I_f}{4 L^3} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^4 a_n^2 \quad \dots (6)$$

The total energy of deformation of the elastic continuum is

$$\Delta U_2 = \frac{B}{2} \int_0^L y^2 dx$$

$$\Delta U_2 = \frac{B L}{4} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n^2 \quad \dots (7)$$

where B is a measure of the elastic continuum's stiffness per unit length of fiber.

The work done by the compressive forces, P, is

$$\Delta T = \frac{P \pi^2}{4 L} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 a_n^2 \quad \dots (8)$$

Since $\Delta T = \Delta U_1 + \Delta U_2$

$$P = \frac{\pi^2 E_f I_f}{L^2} \left[\frac{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^4 a_n^2 + \frac{BL^4}{\pi^4 E_f I_f} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n^2}{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 a_n^2} \right]$$

Critical stress is found when all coefficients, a_n , except one are set equal to zero.

$$P_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 E_f I_f}{L^2} \left[n^2 + \frac{BL^4}{n^2 \pi^4 E_f I_f} \right] \quad \dots (9)$$

$$S_{cr} = \frac{v_f \pi^2 E_f I_f}{A_f L^2} \left[1 + \frac{E_m}{E_f} \right] \left[n^2 + \frac{BL^4}{n^2 \pi^4 E_f I_f} \right] \quad \dots (10)$$

where n is the number of microbuckle halfwaves.

Equation (10) calculates a minimum microbuckle S_{cr} for any fiber in a continuous fiber reinforced flat plate given a specific set of fiber/matrix/composite properties, v_f , n and B . However, the fiber of greatest interest is that which fails under the lowest compressive load and initiates general collapse. A finite element analysis was used to identify outer layer corner fibers as those which have the lowest level transverse support and would be first to fail in a microbuckle. See figure (9). It follows that equation (10) predicts general failure in certain composite flat plates when it is applied to corner fibers.

In addition, during the experiments reported in references [7] and [8], it was observed that the first fibers to fail in a standard ASTM flat plate sample under compression were in the outer layers and at the corners. Following failure at the corners, other fibers along the long side outer layers proceeded to fracture until general collapse occurred. This observation was documented on video tape, and provides further confirmation that the corner fibers are first to fail and are the precursors to general failure.

Figure 9. Finite Element Analysis Model for Evaluating Transverse Support of ASTM Test Sample Corner Fibers

2.4 Microbuckle Stress Predictions in Carbon/Epoxy and Fiber-glass/Epoxy Flat Plate Samples In order to verify equation (10), critical microbuckle stresses were calculated for several carbon/epoxy and fiberglass/epoxy flat plate test samples. See table (1). Evaluated were unidirectional S2-glass/3501-6 epoxy (wall thickness = 0.635 and 1.27 cm), [0/0/90] S2-glass/3501-6 epoxy (wall thickness = 0.635, 1.27 and 2.54 cm), unidirectional AS4-carbon/3501-6 epoxy (wall thickness = 0.3175, 0.635 and 1.27 cm) and [0/0/90] AS4-carbon/3501-6 epoxy (wall thickness = 0.635, 1.27 and 2.54 cm). V_f , for all samples, was taken to be 0.60.

The axial moduli of elasticity used for S2-glass and AS4-carbon fibers were 82.74 GPa and 206.84 GPa respectively. The transverse moduli were 82.74 GPa for glass and 13.79 GPa for carbon. The modulus of elasticity for 3501-6 epoxy was 4.27 GPa. All Poisson's ratios, including values for the composites, were taken to be 0.30. These values were taken from the literature.

Transverse composite Young's moduli were calculated from a fiber/matrix finite element model. The form of the model was verified by AS4/3501-6 transverse property test data collected by Hercules Corporation. For S2-glass/3501-6 epoxy, the modulus was calculated to be 17.37 GPa. For AS4-carbon/3501-6 epoxy, the modulus was calculated to be 10.00 GPa. These transverse moduli were found to be the same for both unidirectional composites and [0/0/90] composites of the same fiber/matrix type and content. Experimental data developed at Oak Ridge National Laboratory verified these similarities. The composite moduli were provided as properties in finite element models of ASTM test sample cross-sections. These models were made up of .25 inch square plane stress elements and used to calculate B.

Table 1. Summary of Microbuckle Stresses, S_{cr} and Fiber/Matrix Stiffness, B, Given $V_f = 0.6$

	S2/3501-6		AS4/3501-6	
Critical stress/ Wall Thickness	[0]	[0/0/90]	[0]	[0/0/90]
S_{cr} in MPa/ .3175 cm (B in Kg/cm)	----	----	1743.8 (2828.2)	----
S_{cr} in MPa/ .6350 cm (B in Kg/cm)	1080.2 (2882.6)	1080.2 (2882.6)	1233.1 (1414.1)	1233.1 (1414.1)
S_{cr} in MPa/ 1.270 cm (B in Kg/cm)	763.8 (1441.3)	763.8 (1441.3)	871.9 (707)	871.9 (707)
S_{cr} in MPa/ 2.540 cm (B in Kg/cm)	----	540.1 (720.7)	----	616.5 (353.5)

See figures (10) and (11) for a comparisons of critical micro-buckling stresses presented in Table (1) with observed failure stresses, references [7] and [8].

FIG 10. CRITICAL COMPRESSIVE STRESS
S-2 FIBERGLASS/3501-6 EPOXY (60/40)
(ENERGY SOLN. FOR COMPRESSIVE FAILURE)

FIG 11. CRITICAL COMPRESSIVE STRESS
AS4 GRAPHITE/3501-6 EPOXY (60/40)
(ENERGY SOLN. FOR COMPRESSIVE FAILURE)

3. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The results obtained from equation (10) are very encouraging. The solutions are reflective of experimental results with respect to both critical stress levels and fall-off with increasing wall thickness. These results indicate that there is a potential for the development of a general approach to the evaluation of ultimate compressive strength in continuous fiber reinforced composites.

The problems to be addressed in future work include unidirectional flat samples with biaxial loading; and [0/0/90] flat samples with biaxial loading. They also include cylinders with various winding formats and wall thicknesses - loaded uniaxially; biaxially; and with moments superimposed. A more detailed finite element model will be developed to evaluate composite mechanical properties and to investigate the interaction between fibers and resins in order to better assess the stiffness of the transverse support in various geometries and formats. In addition, tests to failure will be performed on a series of continuous fiber reinforced composites, including flat samples and right circular cylinders of various thicknesses and laminate formats in order to provide verification of analytical results.

4. REFERENCES

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